

Germplasm improvement

Genetic resources

A new collection of *Oryza officinalis* species from western Uttar Pradesh, India

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We collected 41 seed samples of wild rices: *Oryza nivara* (30), *O. rufipogon* (8), *O. spontanea* (2), and *O. officinalis* (1) in the Uttar Pradesh (UP) districts of Sonbhadra, Mirzapur, Allahabad, Fatehpur, Kanpur, Kanpur Dehat, Farukhabad, Badaun, Moradabad, Rampur, Bareilly, Shahjahanpur, Sitapur, Lucknow, Barabanky, Raibareilly, Faizabad, Sultanpur, Partapgarh, Jaunpur, Azamgarh, Ghazipur, and Mau.

On this exploration, *O. officinalis* was collected from UP for the first time in addition to being found in areas of Saujanpur village, block Miaun, district Badaun, where rice is not traditionally grown. We characterized this accession of *O. officinalis* (JBT10/SP-41) for different morphological traits (see table).

Seeds were sown in pots. Data on five plants were recorded and averaged. Plant height was intermediate and culms erect. Leaves were pubescent and horizontal in angle, and the panicles long and well exerted. The spikelets had awns with no pigmentation. The ligule was acute, long, and light green. No pigmentation was observed in the leaf blade, leaf sheath

Morphological traits of *Oryza officinalis* collected from western Uttar Pradesh, India.

Plant height (cm)	108.5
Leaf length (cm)	42.5
Leaf width (cm)	1.5
Flag leaf length (cm)	37.0
Flag leaf width (cm)	1.6
Effective tillers/hill (no.)	12
Panicle length (cm)	27.6
Primary branches (no.)	7
Secondary branches (no.)	22
Spikelets/panicle (no.)	145
Spikelet length (mm)	6
Spikelet width (mm)	2.3
Awn length (cm)	5.0
Ligule length (mm)	8.0

base, node, and apiculus. The collar and auricle were pale green. Purple lines were observed in internodes and stigma were deeply pigmented. The sterile lemmas were light brown.

The material was not evaluated for resistance to biotic stresses and tolerance

Genetics

Fine mapping of major genes for blast resistance in rice

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Major genes for rice blast resistance *Pi-1(t)*, *Pi-2(t)*, and *Pi-4(t)* have been mapped previously on chromosome 11, 6, and 12, respectively (Yu et al 1991, TAG 81:471-476). *Pi-1(t)* is reported to be linked to RFLP marker RZ536 with a distance of 14.0 ± 4.5 cM, *Pi-2(t)* is closely linked to RG64 with a distance of 2.8 ± 1.4 cM, and *Pi-4(t)* is 15.4 ± 4.7 cM from RG869 and 18.1 ± 5.5 cM from RZ397. The distances between the markers and *Pi-1(t)* and *Pi-4(t)* are relatively large when compared with *Pi-2(t)*. On the other hand, flanking markers for *Pi-2(t)* have not yet been determined. Tightly linked markers are needed for marker-aided breeding because they facilitate early selection of resistance genes in breeding programs.

Recently, more molecular markers were added to the rice RFLP map. With the saturation of the rice map, the probability of identifying markers more closely linked to the resistance genes has increased. In this study, we fine-mapped the three major genes using RFLP

for abiotic stresses. It may, however, have useful genes that could be used in breeding programs to improve modern rice cultivars.

The seeds have been sent for safety duplicate storage at IRRI. ■

markers (RG, RZ, and CDO) from Cornell University, USA, and NpB from the National Institute of Agricultural Resources, Japan.

We selected at least 9 RFLP markers close to the region of the blast resistance genes in the chromosome (see table). To identify more polymorphism in the parental survey, we included more restriction enzymes in addition to the five enzymes previously tested. Three mapping populations (F_2 and F_3) were derived from crosses between the recurrent parent (CO 39) and each of the these isolines. DNA samples were extracted from the fresh leaf tissues collected from the F_2 and F_3 mapping populations, CO 39, isolines, and the donor parents (see table). The DNA extracted from the parents and isolines was used for the parental survey filters, and the extracted DNA from the F_2 plants and F_3 lines (15-20 bulked plants/line) for verification filters for linkage analysis.

The F_3 mapping populations were test-inoculated with IRRI blast isolates 101 and V89013 in two separate trials. At least 15 plants per family were grown and inoculated 21 d after sowing. Disease reaction was evaluated 7 d after inoculation and individual plants of an F_3 family were scored as resistant or susceptible based on disease reaction. A family with both resistant and susceptible plants was

Number of plant materials, restriction enzymes, and RFLP markers used in Southern hybridization.

Blast resistance gene	Isoline	Donor parent	Population size	Restriction enzymes tested	RFLP markers tested	Polymorphic markers
<i>Pi-1(t)</i>	C101LAC	Lac23	160	30	10	5
<i>Pi-2(t)</i>	C101A51	5173	120	12	9	5
<i>Pi-4(t)</i>	C101PKT	Pai-kan-tao	80 ^a	30	14	6

^a F_3 lines were used to represent the F_2 genotypes.